

School Effectiveness And Students' Academic Achievement

Mohamed El Taher Osman, Abdo Mohammed Al-Mekhlafi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 25, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: May 26, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : School Effectiveness, Students, Academic, Schools</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7974852</p>	<p><i>School Effectiveness Studies show that school effectiveness factors can also determine the academic performance and the academic achievement of students. Nyagosia et al. (2013) studied the relationship between school effectiveness factors and academic performance in Kenya, and tried to examine how the implementation of the correlates of effectiveness influenced the academic performance of students. They selected seven correlates formulated by Lezotte (2010 as cited in Nyagosia et al 2013: p.2) are 'instructional leadership, focus on school mission, school safety and orderliness, expectations for success, home-school relations, monitoring students' progress, and opportunity to learn'. Moreover, the findings of school effectiveness studies in Kenya by Nyagosia (2013: p.9) point out that 'the data analysis showed that seven correlates are good predictors of academic performance in Kenyan schools and the results showed that, in comparison with low achieving schools, high performing schools were putting more emphasis on six of the seven correlates with only frequent monitoring of students' progress returning no significant results'.</i></p>

Introduction

Wikipedia defines that academic achievement is the outcome of education- the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their education goals. Academic achievement refers to students' successive stages of their performance in achieving their short-or-long-term goals. It means that students complete exams to earn a degree and it is commonly measured by formative and summative assessments but there is no general agreement on how it is best tested or which aspects are very important. This part of the paper discusses some of the aspects of academic achievement, the factors responsible for academic achievement, the strategies of academic achievement, and shows the relationship between school effectiveness and academic achievement, school improvement and academic achievement, and the ISW and academic achievement.

5.1. Aspects of Academic Achievement

One question that preoccupies the researchers is why some educational institutions are characterized by high performance and why others are characterized by poor performance. Many studies have been carried out to identify the effective factors for attaining and enhancing academic achievement. All school effectiveness studies on correlates and school improvement research on SI framework illustrate the fact that high performing schools have unique characteristics and processes which enable all students and staff to perform better. Academic achievement is a key concern for many educators, parents and children because failure in examinations spells doom for children and prevents them from pursuing higher education. As a student's life is determined by his/her academic achievement, people involved in school education are constantly involved in adopting innovative ways to make their schools competitive and high performing institutions.

Most researchers studied the academic performance of students from various perspectives. Campbell (2007: p.1) 'explored the validity of the Motivational Systems Theory (MST) as a measure of performance of college students pursuing business studies. He investigated the relationships between motivational strategies, biological factors, responsive environment factors, skill/prior ability, and academic performance of the students and the impact on the level of academic performance by the college students' gender and race'. The results indicated that the motivational systems theory is a valid indicator of academic performance and strongly supported the claim that certain variables such as gender and race can exert an influence on the levels of college performance of students. The result of the study provided an evidence to justify Ford's Motivational Systems Theory (as cited in Campbell: 2007 p.2) which is given below:

$$\text{Performance / Achievement} = \frac{(\text{Motivational skill}) \times \text{Responsive Environment}}{\text{Biological Structure}}$$

The findings of this study provide some evidence for considering motivational components which can enhance the academic performance of students. However, the implementation of motivational systems

alone cannot guarantee high levels of academic performance. Consequently, educational institutions need to integrate a set of several components in order to enhance the academic performance of students. Many researchers have tried to identify the differences between academic achievement and academic performance.

The concepts 'academic performance' 'academic achievement,' and 'learning outcomes' refer to different levels of observable and quantifiable academic behavior of students. Yusuf (p.5) in his feedback of Lawrence's (1998) review of 'the manufactured crisis' distinguished academic performance and academic achievement. From his viewpoint, *'In relation to educational research, academic performance of a student can be regarded as the observable and measurable behavior of a student in a particular situation'*. On the other hand, *academic achievement is measured in relation to what is attained at the end of a course, since it is the accomplishment of medium or long term objective of education'*. What he means is that academic achievement is a long term end while academic performance is measurable at any point in time. In other words, academic achievement is a final outcome or product and academic performance refers to a set of activities involved in an ongoing process. Therefore, many academicians use the academic performance index in their educational institutions. The index is a set of activities which students perform to improve their skills and competencies. This illustrates the fact that academic achievement is cumulative and progressive., and it cannot be attained within a short period of time.

Several studies were conducted in the United States of America with an aim to show that the ongoing academic performance of students lead to academic achievement. The researchers compared the academic performance of home schooled students to national standards. According to Theodore (1995 as cited in Yusuf: p.9), *'it was discovered that home schooled students who perform well also do well in the standardized academic test'*. This indicates clearly that academic performance of learners exerts a tremendous influence on academic achievement. Shin-Yin and James (2001 as cited in Yusuf p.9), *'compared the academic performance and the academic achievement of Chinese, Japanese and American students in mathematics. The students' performance in perceptual speed, coding skill, spatial abilities, vocabulary, verbal memory and general information was measured and the findings show that the Chinese and Japanese performed much better in mathematics than the American students'*. This shows clearly that there are several aspects of academic performance in subjects taught in schools and they affect the academic achievement of students.

Glass (1994 as cited in Yusuf: p.10) compared the academic performance of New Jersey's public school children with those children from other participating states. *'It was argued that for most plausible questions about performance of the public schools the standardized scores were more reliable and useful for knowing the academic achievement of students. This again confirms the earlier finding that academic performance is short term and can be teacher made test scores, while achievement is medium or long term and they are standardized test scores'*. In the light of the discussions, the researchers synthesize a viable definition of academic achievement. It is defined as different levels of academic performance leading to academic success. It involves the achievement of the learning outcomes, the competencies and skills, the course objectives and the levels of academic performance. The academic achievement refers to the completion of high school or earning a college degree and it is the different levels of academic performance that culminate in academic achievement. In other words, the academic achievement of students is a fruit of a dynamic interplay between learning outcomes, course objectives, competencies, skills, and values, and academic performance. According to Gosselin et al (2013: p.1) *'Competencies are general statements which refer to skills, knowledge that enable students to successfully perform in professional and educational contexts. The learning outcomes refer to specific skills, abilities, and knowledge which the students will be able to achieve at the end of a course'*. The course objectives refer to what the teachers are expected to do for a successful completion of a course. It is schematically shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Model of Academic Achievement

5.2. Factors Responsible for Academic Achievement

Researchers in education have identified several factors that have influence on how students perform in an educational system. These factors vary from place to place and from one institution to another. However, a large number of factors are common to all students and institutions. Mlambo (2011: p.3-5) identified the following four major factors:

- Student learning preferences and teaching styles
- Class Attendance and Exam Performance
- Entry Qualifications and Prerequisites
- Other determinants (Age and gender) of Academic performance

Several studies were conducted in West Indian Universities. Their findings identify that factors such as students' effort, previous schooling, parents' education, socio-economic status, self-motivation, students' age, and learning styles have tremendous effect on students' academic performance in various settings. According to Mlambo (2011: p.3), *'although there has been considerable debate about the determinants of academic performance among educators, policy makers, academicians and other stakeholders, it is generally agreed that the impact of these determinants vary (in terms of extent and direction) with context, for example, culture, institution, course of study etc. Since all factors are relevant for a particular context, it is imperative that formal studies be carried out to identify the context-specific determinants for sound decision making'*.

5.2.1. School Improvement and Academic Achievement

Research studies conducted on school improvement bring to light several improvement factors responsible for an ongoing development of schools. The most popular school improvement factors include project-based learning, integrated studies, cooperative learning, comprehensive assessment, teachers as intellectual guides, teaching as apprenticeship, adopting new technology, organizing resources, and involving parents and community partners. All these ways of school improvement can have a tremendous impact on the academic achievement of students. For example, project-based learning can help students develop a wide variety of skills and improve their competencies. In the same way each improvement factor can play a positive role in enhancing academic achievement.

The ISW is centered on a dynamic academic leadership; therefore, it is intended to activate several driving forces (Figure 5). Moreover, it can be clearly seen that the ISW has all the potential to enhance school effectiveness and school improvement which lead to greater academic achievement. Consequently, it is valid

hunch that the application of the ISW in schools in Oman can effect tremendous changes in educational systems, and enable students to achieve excellence in academics.

Figure 22 ISW and Academic achievement

Figure 22 shows that each driving force of the ISW can influence an educational institution in such a way that it can result in a great deal of academic achievement and promote a dynamic interplay between academic performance of students, learning outcomes, and certain competencies and values that can lead to greater academic achievement.

References

- Campbell, J. R., C. M. Hombo, and J. Mazzeo. (2000). *NAEP 1999 Trends in Academic Progress: Three Decades of Student Performance*. NCES 2000-469. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics.
- Campbell, M.M(2007) Motivational Systems Theory and The Academic Performance of College Students. <http://clutejournals.com/index.php/TLC/article/download/1561/1541>
Retrieved in January 2019
- Ford, M. (1992). *Motivating humans: Goals, emotions, and personal agency beliefs*. NewBury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- Glass, G., Cohen, L., Smith.M., & Tilby, N. (1982) *School Class Size*. Beverley Hills CA. Sage.
- Gosselin, D., Cooper, S., Bonnstetter, R.J., & Bonnstetter, B.J. (2013) *Competencies and Learning Outcomes*. Retrieved from [Exploring the assessment of twenty-first century professional competencies of undergraduate students in environmental studies through a business—academic partnership](http://exploringtheassessmentoftwenty-firstcenturyprofessionalcompetenciesofundergraduatestudentsinenvironmentalstudiesthroughabusinessacademicpartnership) in May 2019
- Jamillah. M. (2016) *Factors affecting students' academic performance: a case study of public secondary schools in Ilala district, Dar Es-Salaam, Tanzania*. Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/79425366.pdf>
- Kirk, D. J. & Jones, T. L. (2004). *Effective schools assessment report*. San Antonio, TX: Pearson Education. http://images.pearsonassessments.com/images/tmrs/tmrs_rg/EffectiveSchools.pdf
- Kapur, R (2018) 'Factors Influencing the Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in India'. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324819919_Factors_Influencing_the_Students_Academic_Performance_in_Secondary_Schools_in_India in November 2018
- Lawrence, C. S. (1998). *Review of the manufactured crisis*. ACC-VE 2001.
- Lezotte, L. (1991). *Correlates of effective schools: the first and second generation*. Okemos, MI: Effective Schools Products, Ltd.
- Lezotte, L. (2001). *Revolutionary and evolutionary: the effective schools movement*. Okemos, MI: Effective Schools Products, Ltd.
- Mlambo., V. (2011) *An analysis of some factors affecting student academic performance in an introductory biochemistry course at the University of the West Indies Caribbean Teaching Scholar* Vol. 1, No. 2, November 79–

http://scholar.google.com/scholar_url?url=https://journals.sta.uwi.edu/ojs/index.php/cts/article/download/10/7&hl=en&sa=X&scisig=AAGBfm1zmgdYNFA0-X0n404paxmoakODFA&nossl=1&oi=scholar

in May 2018

Mushtaq, I., & Khan, S.K., 2012 Factors affecting student performance:

Global Journal of Management and Business Research Volume 12 Issue 9 Version 1.0

Type: Double Blind Peer Reviewed International Research Journal

Publisher: Global Journals Inc. (USA)

Online ISSN: 2249-4588 & Print ISSN: 0975-5853

Nyagosia. P.O., Waweru, S.N., Felicitaw. & Njuguna (2013) Factors influencing academic achievement in public secondary schools in central Kenya: an effective schools' perspective

https://www.academia.edu/20181566/FACTORS_THAT_AFFECT_STUDENTS_ACADEMIC_PERFORMANCE_A_CASE_STUDY_OF_SECONDARY_SCHOOLS_IN_CENTRAL_PROVINCE_KENYA

Theodore, E. W. Jr (1995). Academic achievement in the home school. *Gazelle Publication* (pp. 25 - 26)

Yusuf, A. Inter-relationship Among Academic Performance, Academic Achievement and Learning outcomes.

Retrieved from

http://musero.org.ng/publications/inter-relationship_among_academic_performance_academic_achievement_learning_outcomes.pdf

In February 2019

Author Information

Mohamed El Taher Osman

College of Education, Sultan Qaboos University,
Sultanate of Oman

Abdo Mohammed Al-Mekhlafi

College of Education, Sultan Qaboos University,
Sultanate of Oman
